

A Study On Association Of Autoimmune Diseases With Chronic Urticaria In Tertiary Teaching Hospital

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ABSTRACT

Background: Urticaria is a mast cell – mediated dermatological condition characterized by recurrent transient, itchy, raised wheals and sometimes deeper swelling known as angioedema. Chronic urticaria lasts more than six weeks and significantly affects quality of life. Evidence shows strong association with autoimmune diseases especially thyroid disorders and it shows many chronic urticaria cases have autoimmune basis. Common associations include thyroid autoimmunity, rheumatoid arthritis, alopecia, celiac disease, and other auto immune disorders. Autoantibodies against IgE or its receptors are frequently reported. Thyroid screening is widely recommended. **Aims and Objectives:** To evaluate the association between autoimmune diseases and chronic urticaria. To investigate the incidence of autoimmune diseases in chronic urticaria. To identify specific autoimmune diseases associated with chronic urticaria. To improve diagnosis and management of autoimmune related chronic urticaria. To asses impact on quality of life and mental health. **Materials and Methods:** A prospective Observational study was conducted over six months (November 2024–April 2025) in the departments of Dermatology, at Sri Balaji Medical College Hospital, Tirupati. A total of 70 patients diagnosed with chronic urticaria were enrolled in the study. Patients of all age groups and both genders with chronic urticaria were included, while pregnant women, patients with acute urticaria and those with allergy-induced urticaria were excluded. Data were collected using a structured data collection form that included demographic details, clinical history, duration and severity of urticaria, associated symptoms, laboratory investigations and treatment details patients were evaluated for the presence of autoimmune diseases, particularly thyroid disorders, through relevant clinical assessments and laboratory tests. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive statistical methods such as mean and standard deviation and appropriate tests were applied using MS Excel to determine. **Results:** A total of 70 subjects with chronic urticaria were included in the study. The gender distribution was almost equal, with 51% males and 49% females. The most commonly affected age group was 31-40 years. Itching was the most frequent symptom, reported in 62% of subjects. Angioedema was observed in 21% of the cases. Approximately 39% of subjects had associated autoimmune diseases. Autoimmune thyroid disorder was the most common association, seen in 23% of subjects. **Conclusion:** Chronic urticaria shows a significant association with autoimmune diseases particularly autoimmune thyroid disorders. The presence of autoimmune conditions contributes to increased disease chronicity and symptom severity. Routine screening of autoimmune diseases in patients with chronic urticaria can aid in early diagnosis and improved management. Early identification of autoimmune involvement helps in selecting appropriate and personalised treatment strategies. Chronic urticaria should be considered a systemic condition rather than only a dermatological disorder. Multidisciplinary and individualised care is essential to improve patient outcomes and quality of life.

Keywords: Chronic Urticaria; Autoimmune Diseases; Thyroiditis; Angioedema; Autoimmunity; Antihistamines; Mast cell activation.

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INTRODUCTION

Urticaria is a common dermatological skin condition with systemic pathogenic involvement that is expressed in the skin and in the mucous membranes in a very special way with erythema, edema, and pruritus and with the basic individuality that the lesions are quickly fading for a short time [1]. Urticaria is a mast cell-mediated skin condition characterized by transient, itchy wheals and sometimes angioedema. Before diagnosing it, clinicians must rule out other causes such as anaphylaxis, inflammatory diseases, UV-induced edema, or bradykinin-mediated swelling [2]. Angioneurotic oedema is a related condition causing deeper, larger swelling in the dermis, subcutaneous tissue, and mucous membranes. Also called angioedema, giant urticaria, or Quincke's oedema, it involves more extensive tissue swelling than typical urticaria [3]. Urticaria is classified into three main types: spontaneous (80%), physical (10%), and special forms (<10%). Spontaneous urticaria includes acute (lasting <6 weeks, often infection- or drug-related), chronic (>6 weeks, may persist for years, often autoimmune or idiopathic), and episodic (intermittent flare-ups over time). Physical urticaria is triggered by external stimuli and includes dermatographism, delayed pressure, cold, heat, solar, and vibratory urticaria each induced by specific physical factors like pressure, temperature, light, or vibration. Special forms are not due to external physical forces and include cholinergic (heat/exercise-induced), exercise-induced, aquagenic (water contact), and contact urticaria, all involving mast cell-mediated histamine release [4]. The causes may be divided into three categories: Immunoglobulin E (IgE) mediated, non-IgE immunologically mediated, and non-immunologically mediated factors. IgE-mediated causes include aeroallergens, contact allergens, food allergens, insect venom, medications, and parasitic infections. Non-IgE immunologically mediated causes include aeroallergens (such as proteases), autoimmune diseases, bacterial infections, cryoglobulinemia, fungal infections, lymphoma, vasculitis, and viral infections. Non immunologically mediated causes include contact allergens, elevation of core body temperature, food pseudo-allergens, light exposure, mastocytosis, medications that directly cause mast cell degranulation, physical

stimuli such as cold, heat, pressure, and vibration, as well as water exposure [5]. The risk factors include food allergies, drug reactions, insect bites, infections, contact allergies, inhalant allergens, and idiopathic causes. Physical factors such as exposure to cold, hot showers, sweating, exercise, dermatographism, pressure, solar exposure, and water can also increase the risk [6]. Urticaria occurs due to activation of mast cells in the skin, leading to the release of histamine. Histamine causes redness, swelling, and itching by increasing vascular permeability and stimulating nerve endings. Basophils may contribute to delayed or prolonged reactions, especially in chronic urticaria. Inflammatory cells like neutrophils, eosinophils, and T-cells can further enhance mast cell activation. In some cases, autoantibodies against IgE, FcεRI, or C5a trigger mast cell degranulation, causing autoimmune urticaria [7]. Urticaria is diagnosed mainly through clinical history, classified as acute (<6 weeks) or chronic (>6 weeks), with lesions usually resolving within 24 hours. Most chronic cases have no identifiable trigger, though drugs and autoimmune diseases may be involved. Examination shows raised, pruritic wheals with erythema, sometimes with angioedema. Differential diagnoses include urticarial vasculitis, cryoglobulinemia, and mastocytosis. Laboratory tests are rarely needed, but thyroid function, ANA, and specialized tests like the Autologous Serum Skin Test can help in atypical or autoimmune cases [8]. Management of chronic urticaria involves identifying and avoiding triggers, treating infections, and managing underlying conditions. Patient education, symptom diaries, and lifestyle modifications, including stress reduction and dietary adjustments, are important. Second-generation non-sedating H1 antihistamines are the main pharmacological treatment, with omalizumab, cyclosporine, or montelukast used for resistant cases. Short-term corticosteroids are reserved for acute flares, while long-term use is avoided due to side effects. Angioedema is managed based on type: histamine-mediated cases use antihistamines, corticosteroids, or epinephrine, while non-histamine-mediated forms require C1 inhibitors, bradykinin antagonists, or treatment of the underlying cause [9].

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

It is a Prospective study and was conducted in departments of Sri balaji medical care hospital (SBMHC), Renigunta, Tirupati. The study was exploratory in nature; therefore, descriptive statistical methods were primarily used. The study was carried out on patients diagnosed with chronic urticaria, of all age groups and both genders with chronic urticaria were included, while pregnant women, patients with acute urticaria and those with allergy-induced urticaria were excluded. The study was conducted for a period of 6 months from November 2024 to April 2025. A total of 70 subjects of Dermatology departments were enrolled in the study after evaluating for inclusion and exclusion criteria. The purpose of the study was explained and written informed consent was obtained from all the participants. Data for this study were collected using a structured data collection form designed to ensure systematic and comprehensive recording of relevant information. The form included demographic details (age, gender, occupation), clinical history (onset, duration, and previous episodes of urticaria), duration and severity of urticaria, and associated symptoms such as angioedema, pruritus, or systemic manifestations. In addition, information on laboratory investigations and treatment history (type of medications, duration, and clinical response) was documented for each patient. All participants were evaluated for the presence of autoimmune disorders,

with particular attention to thyroid diseases. This evaluation included clinical assessments and laboratory investigations, such as thyroid function tests and measurement of thyroid-specific autoantibodies, to identify any underlying autoimmune associations. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive statistical methods, including calculation of mean, standard deviation, and frequency distributions, to summarize patient characteristics and clinical findings. Furthermore, appropriate inferential statistical tests were applied using MS Excel to assess relationships between variables and determine the statistical significance of observed associations. This structured approach facilitated a clear and meaningful interpretation of the study results.

RESULTS:

A total of 70 Chronic Urticaria patients were recruited in our study, out of 70 subjects, 43 subjects were not associated with any autoimmune diseases, 16 subjects were associated with Thyroiditis, 5 subjects were associated with Rheumatoid arthritis, 5 subjects were associated with Alopecia and 1 subject were associated with Celiac disease. Out of 70 subjects 36 were male population and 34 were female population explains distribution of subjects based on gender in [Table 1].

Table 1: Shows distribution of subjects based on gender.

S. No	Gender	No. of Subjects (N=70)	Percentage (%)
1.	Male	36	51
2.	Female	34	49
	Total	70	100

The average age of the study population was 36 years, with males averaging 38 years and females 34 years. Most subjects were in the 31–40 years age group (29/70), followed by 15–30 years (20/70) and 41–50 years (16/70). Few subjects were in the 51–60 years (4/70) and 60–70 years (1/70) age groups explain distribution of age group in total study sample in [Table 2].

Table 2: Shows distribution of subjects based on their age group.

S. No	Age Group (In Years)	Males (N=36)	Females (N=34)	No. of Subjects (N=70)	Percentage (%)	P Value
1.	15-30	8	12	20	29	
2.	31-40	16	13	29	41	

3.	41-50	8	8	16	23	0.006
4.	51-60	3	1	4	6	
5.	61-70	1	0	1	1	
Total		36	34	70	100	
Mean Age		38	34	36		
SD±		5.805	6.058	11.55		

The study population of 70 subjects was categorized by occupation, with the largest groups being housewives (17) and students (15). Employees numbered 11, followed by teachers (6) and farmers

(4). Smaller groups included electricians and business persons (3 each), plumbers, carpenters, and drivers (2 each) explain the distribution based on occupation in total study sample in [Table 3].

Table 3: Shows distribution of subjects based on occupation.

S. No	Type of Occupation	No. of Subjects (N=70)	Percentage (%)
1	Students	15	21
2	House Wife	17	24
3	Farmer	4	6
4	Employee	11	16
5	Teacher	6	9
6	Plumber	2	3
7	Barber	1	1
8	Accountant	1	1
9	Carpenter	2	3
10	Business	3	5
11	Mechanic	1	1
12	Electrician	3	5
13	Security Guard	1	1
14	Driver	2	3
15	Contractor	1	1
Total		70	100

Out of 70 subjects, 43 subjects were not presented with any autoimmune diseases, 16 subjects were presented with thyroiditis, 5 subjects were presented with rheumatoid arthritis, 5 subjects were presented with

alopecia and 1 subject were presented with celiac explains the distribution based on history of autoimmune diseases in total study sample in [Table 4].

Table 4: Shows distribution of subjects based on history of autoimmune diseases associated in Chronic Urticaria.

S. No	Type Of Autoimmune Diseases	Males (N=36)	Females (N=34)	No. of Subjects (N=70)	Percentage (%)
1.	Thyroiditis	07	08	16	23
2.	Rheumatoid Arthritis	01	04	05	7
3.	Alopecia	04	02	05	7

4.	Celiac	01	00	01	2
5.	None	23	20	43	61
Total		36	34	70	100

Out of 70 subjects, 28 subjects were having urticaria on all over body, 12 subjects were having urticaria on neck, 11 subjects were having urticaria on upper limb, 10 subjects were having urticaria on lower limb, 8

subjects were having urticaria on face and 1 subject was having urticaria on trunk explain the distribution based on location of urticaria in total study sample in [Table 5].

Table 5: Shows distribution of subjects based on location of urticaria.

S. No	Location	No. of Subjects (N=70)	Percentage (%)
1	Face	8	11
2	Neck	12	17
3	Trunk	1	1
4	Upper Limb	11	16
5	Lower Limb	10	14
6	All Over Body	28	41
Total		70	100

Out of 70 subjects, 43 subjects presented with itching symptom, 15 subjects presented with angioedema, 7 subjects presented with redness, and 5 subjects

presented with rashes explain the distribution based on clinical features of chronic urticaria in total study sample in [Table 6].

Table 6: Shows distribution of subjects based on clinical features of urticaria.

S. No	Types Of Symptoms	No. of Subjects (N=70)	Percentage (%)
1	Only Itching	43	62
2	Angioedema with Itching	15	21
3	Redness with Itching	7	10
4	Rashes with Itching	5	7
Total		70	100

Out of 70 subjects, 36 subjects were presented with wheals in that 13 were males and 23 were females and 34 subjects were presented with hives in

that 23 were males and 11 were females explain the distribution based on types of lesions in total study sample in [Table 7].

Table 7: Shows distribution of subjects based on types of lesions in Chronic Urticaria.

S. No	Type Of Lesions	Males (N=36)	Females (N=34)	No. of Subjects (N=70)	Percentage (%)
1.	Hives	23	11	34	49
2.	Wheals	13	23	36	51
Total		36	34	70	100

Out of 70 subjects, 52 subjects were not associated with angioedema in that 31 were males and 21 were female subjects and 18 subjects were associated with

angioedema in that 05 were males and 13 were female subjects explain the distribution based on chronic urticaria association with angioedema and without angioedema in total study population in [Table 8].

Table 8: Shows distribution of subjects based on chronic urticaria associated with angioedema and without angioedema in Chronic Urticaria male and female subjects.

S. No	Type	Males (N=36)	Females (N=34)	No. of Subjects (N=70)	Percentage (%)
1.	With Angioedema	05	13	18	26
2.	Without Angioedema	31	21	52	74
	Total	36	34	70	100

Out of 70 subjects, 23 subjects have duration from 1-2 years, 16 subjects have duration from 3-12 months, 13 subjects have duration from 3-5 years, 11 subjects have duration of disease from 5-10 weeks, 04 subjects

have duration from 6-8 years, 02 subjects have duration from 09-12 years and 01 subject have duration from 13-15 years explain the distribution based on duration of chronic urticaria in total study population in [Table 9]

Table 9: Shows distribution of subjects based on duration of Chronic Urticaria.

S. No	Duration	Males (N=36)	Females (N=34)	Total No. of subjects (N=70)	Percentage (%)
1	05-10 Weeks	6	5	11	16
2	03-12 Months	7	9	16	23
3	1-2 Years	12	11	23	33
4	3-5 Years	6	7	13	18
5	6-8 Years	3	1	4	6
6	9-12 Years	1	1	2	3
7	13-15 Years	1	0	1	1
	Total	36	34	70	100

Out of 70 subjects, 70 subjects were treated with calamine lotion, 41 subjects were treated with fexofenadine, 40 subjects were treated with montek-lc, 32 subjects were treated with bilastine, 23 subjects

were treated with hydroxyzine and 3 subjects were treated with predmet explains the distribution based on drug therapy in total study sample in [Table 10].

Table 10: Shows distribution of subjects based on drug therapy.

S. No	Drugs	Total No. of Prescription	Percentage (%)
1	Fexofenadine	41	59
2	Montek-Lc	40	57
3	Bilastine	32	46

4	Hydroxyzine	23	33
5	Calamine Lotion	70	100
6	Predmet	3	4

Among 70 subjects, the most commonly used therapy was fexofenadine + montek-LC + calamine lotion (21), followed by bilastine + montek-LC + calamine lotion (16). Moderate use was seen with fexofenadine + hydroxyzine + calamine lotion (13) and bilastine +

hydroxyzine + calamine lotion (9). The least used combinations were fexofenadine + bilastine + calamine lotion (8) and predmet + montek-LC + calamine lotion (3) explains the distribution based on combined drug therapy in total study sample in [Table 11].

Table 11: Shows distribution of subjects based on combined drug therapy in Chronic Urticaria patients.

S. No	Triple Drug Therapy	No. of Subjects (N=70)	Percentage (%)
1.	Fexofenadine +Montek-Lc +Calamine Lotion	21	30
2.	Fexofenadine +Hydroxyzine +Calamine Lotion	13	19
3.	Bilastine +Hydroxyzine +Calamine Lotion	9	13
4.	Predmet +Montek-Lc +Calamine Lotion	3	4
5.	Fexofenadine +Bilastine +Calamine Lotion	8	11
6.	Bilastine +Montek-Lc +Calamine Lotion	16	23
	Total	70	100

DISCUSSION:

This study assessed the prevalence of association between autoimmune diseases and chronic urticaria among 70 patients at Dermatology department in a tertiary care teaching hospital over six months. This study demonstrates that a meaningful proportion of patients with chronic urticaria have coexisting autoimmune diseases, supporting the concept that autoimmune mechanisms contribute to disease pathogenesis in a defined subset of cases. The predominance of autoimmune thyroid disorders observed is consistent with existing evidence, suggesting a clinically relevant link between thyroid autoimmunity and chronic urticaria, potentially mediated through autoantibody-driven mast cell activation. The presence of additional autoimmune conditions further reinforces the notion of underlying systemic immune dysregulation rather than an isolated cutaneous process. The demographic and clinical patterns observed are broadly comparable with prior reports, with pruritus and intermittent angioedema representing the most common

manifestations. From a therapeutic standpoint, the reliance on second-generation antihistamines reflects adherence to current guideline-based management; however, variability in disease course and response highlights the need for individualized treatment strategies, particularly in patients with autoimmune comorbidities. These findings have important clinical pharmacy implications, emphasizing the role of comprehensive patient assessment, optimization of pharmacotherapy, and monitoring for treatment response and adherence. Nevertheless, the study is limited by its modest sample size and single-center design, which may affect generalizability. Overall, the results contribute to the growing body of evidence that chronic urticaria is a heterogeneous condition with a significant autoimmune component, supporting the need for selective screening for autoimmune disorders and a multidisciplinary approach to improve patient outcomes. Due to the exploratory nature of the study and sample size constraints, advanced inferential statistical analysis was not performed. Similar associations have been consistently reported across diverse populations, reinforcing the external validity of these findings.

CONCLUSION:

This prospective study findings revealed that 39% of patients had associated autoimmune diseases, indicating a significant autoimmune contribution to CU. Among these, autoimmune thyroiditis was the most commonly observed comorbidity. However, 61% of patients did not show evidence of any autoimmune disorder, suggesting that multiple mechanisms are involved in the pathogenesis of CU. The majority of patients belonged to the 31–40 years age group, highlighting the higher prevalence in middle-aged adults. Wheals and recurrent hives were the most common presenting symptoms in the study population. A considerable proportion of patients also experienced angioedema along with urticaria. Female patients demonstrated a higher incidence of angioedema compared to males. Thyroid dysfunction was also more prevalent among women, reinforcing the known association between thyroid autoimmunity and CU. The study supports the concept that autoimmune mechanisms play an important but not universal role in chronic urticaria. It emphasizes that CU is a heterogeneous condition with diverse etiological factors. Early screening for autoimmune comorbidities, especially thyroid disorders, is clinically valuable. Prompt identification of associated autoimmune conditions can guide appropriate management strategies. Comprehensive evaluation and individualized treatment can improve symptom control. Ultimately, early diagnosis and targeted therapy can significantly enhance the overall quality of life of patients with chronic urticaria.

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